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THE APPLICATION OF STEEL FIBRES IN HIGH-STRENGTH CONCRETE

Sabah Shawkat

Assoc. Prof., PhD., Academy of Fine Arts and Design in Bratislava, SLOVAKIA, shawkat@vsvu.sk

Abstract

The current aim is to analyse the effects of fibre reinforcement in high-strength concrete (HSC) also known as high-performance concrete (HPC). While HSC excels in applications where compressive strength is crucial, high-strength fibre concrete (HSFC, HPFC) provides enhanced tensile strength and durability, making it suitable for projects where cracking and structural integrity are significant concerns. The choice between them depends on the specific requirements and constraints of a construction project. Currently, fibre reinforcement is increasingly used in concrete structures in addition to traditional reinforcement with concrete and prestressing reinforcement. Its use depends on the type of structure, its shape, load, and environmental conditions. In conclusion, the main reason for the use of fibre reinforcement in concrete is to improve its properties in terms of strength, but also deformation properties and failure mode. Fibre-reinforced (FRC) can be used in the construction of structures for the storage of radioactive waste materials. When dealing with radioactive waste storage, it's crucial to ensure the structural integrity and long-term performance of the containment system. Fibers in the concrete help control the formation and propagation of cracks. This is important for preventing the release of radioactive materials due to cracks in the containment structure.

Keywords: Normal-Strength Concrete, High-Strength, Concrete, Fibre Reinforced Concrete.

1. HIGH-STRENGTH CONCRETE

1.1 Introduction

The maximum design strength of reinforced concrete has changed throughout the years. Back in the 1950s, concrete with a maximum compressive strength of 35 MPa was achieved without the need for any chemical or mineral admixtures. By the 1960s, the commercial use of 50 MPa concrete became attainable. This advancement was closely linked to the development of superplasticizers, which are highly effective chemical admixtures that reduce the water content in concrete while preserving its workability. Moving into the 1970s, there was a growing exploration of combining superplasticizers with ultra-fine materials like silica fume, finely ground blast furnace slag, or anhydrous gypsum-based additives, all of which were studied and applied in the construction of concrete structures (Shawkat. S. Schlesinger. R) and (Shawkat. S). Presently, the upper limit for concrete strength in the construction industry is within the range of 100 to 135 MPa. Figure 1 presents differences in national definitions for upper concrete strength limits due to the local traditions regarding concrete strengths and qualities generally achieved with currently available cement, aggregates, and the available competence and experience of the local workforce.

Over time, there has been a consistent effort to enhance the compressive strength of concrete, primarily to facilitate the construction of taller and more slender structures while maintaining a generous effective floor area. In the process, it became evident that it was possible to customise the microstructure of concrete to achieve not only greater strength but also other advantageous attributes like durability, workability, and toughness. Consequently, the term "high-strength concrete" (HSC) has emerged, wherein the desired level of strength may vary according to specific applications, as detailed in Table 1(Shah, S.P).

Fig. 1. Minor differences in defining High-Strength Concrete (DIN - German standard, Eurocode – EU countries definition, ACI – American Concrete Institute standard) (Shah, S.P)

Table 1. Properties of Concrete (Shah, S.P)

Properties of concrete	Normal Strength Concrete	High Strength Concrete	Ultra-High Strength Concrete
Compressive Strength [MPa]	< 50	> 50 and < 100	> 200
Water-binder Ratio	> 0.40	~ 0.30	< 0.20
Water Reducing Admixture	not necessary	not necessary	essential
Mineral Additive	not necessary	fly ash silica fume commonly used	silica fume fine powder
Fibres	beneficial	beneficial	essential
Processing	conventional	conventional	heat treatment
Steady State Chloride Diffusion ($\times 10^{-12} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	1	0.6	0.02

1.2 Materials

The presence of a weaker region surrounding the aggregate is a well-documented phenomenon in normal-strength concrete (NSC). Consequently, the compressive strength is constrained by both the strength of the paste and the bonding between the paste and aggregate. In the case of High-Strength Concrete (HSC), this bonding is significantly more robust, resulting in exceptional stress transfer capabilities. The strength and modulus of elasticity in HSC, however, face limitations imposed by the modulus of elasticity of the aggregate, as well as the quality of the transition zone.

In theory, when concrete is subjected to compression, the initial development of cracks occurs within the transition zone (Shawkat. S. Schlesinger. R). A microscopic examination of hydrated cement paste (HCP) in NSC reveals a relatively weaker region around the aggregate, characterized by poor stress transfer between the HCP and the aggregate Figure 2 (Mindes, S. & Bentur, A). In essence, the aggregates bear only a minimal portion of these stresses. In the context of NSC, where the water-to-cement (w/c) ratio typically falls within the range of 0.50-0.70, aggregates are often regarded as inert materials used primarily for economic and volumetric stability reasons in the mix (Shawkat. S. Schlesinger. R). Therefore, the strength of concrete is predominantly influenced by the matrix strength (cement paste) enveloping the aggregate particles. Under consistent curing conditions and given the same age, the compressive strength of concrete primarily hinges on the w/c ratio and the type and quality of cement used (Shawkat. S). Any significant increase or decrease in strength is generally attributed to the cement employed.

Fig. 2. Normal-Strength Concrete (Mindes, S. & Bentur, A.)

Fig. 3. High-Strength Concrete HSC (Mindes, S. & Bentur, A.)

In the case of HSC, it is noteworthy that both the paste and the transition zone tend to exhibit greater density and strength compared to NSC, resulting in effective stress transfer between the aggregate and paste (Shawkat. S. Schlesinger. R) and (Shawkat. S). In simpler terms, aggregates in HSC actively contribute to the mechanical behaviour of the concrete. Researchers and industry professionals are increasingly recognizing the crucial role that aggregates play in the development of HSC.

Two key factors of significance in this regard are the strength of the aggregates themselves and the strength of the interface, which refers to the bond between the aggregate and the matrix (Mindes, S. & Bentur, A.). The strength of this bond between hydrated cement paste (HCP) and aggregate depends on factors such as the extent of Ca (OH)₂ crystal formation and the presence of voids or defects at the interface, as illustrated in Figure 3.

The calcium hydroxide, denoted as Ca (OH)₂, which emerges during the cement hydration process, neither enhances strength development nor improves the quality of the transition zone (as depicted in Figure 4) (Chan, S.Y.N.; Anson, M.; Koo, S. L). However, through the incorporation of mineral admixtures like natural pozzolans, silica fume, and fly ash, this calcium hydroxide undergoes a secondary reaction, transforming into calcium silicate hydrates (CSH), which significantly bolsters the strength of both cement and concrete (as illustrated in Figure 5 (Chan, S.Y.N.).

In conclusion, the compressive strength of concrete is constrained by the strength of the paste and the bond between paste and aggregate, factors that can be enhanced through various means, including:

- Reducing the water-to-cement (w/c) ratio, as shown in Figure 6 (Chan, S.Y.N).
- Utilizing an extensive quantity of plasticizers (Chan, S.Y.N).
- Employing high-strength potential cement.
- Incorporating pozzolans and silica fume.

Fig. 4. Normal-Strength Concrete (Mindes, S. & Bentur, A.:)

Fig. 5. High-Strength Concrete (Mindes, S. & Bentur, A.:)

Fig. 6. Influence of w/c Ratio on Strengths

1.3 Silica Fume

Silica fume (SF) is a by-product generated during the process of producing silicon metal and ferrosilicon alloys through melting. SF possesses notable characteristics, including a high content of amorphous SiO₂, ranging from 85% to 98%, an average particle size falling within the range of 0.1 to 0.2 microns, and a spherical shape. SF serves a dual role as both filler and pozzolan (High-Strength Concrete Joint FIP CEB State-of-the-art Report).

When SF is employed as a partial replacement for cement, it results in a substantial increase in strength. In the context of normal-strength concrete (NSC), SF demonstrates an efficiency factor that is 2 to 4 times higher than that of Portland Cement concerning long-term strength. This efficiency factor increases with rising strength requirements. Consequently, the use of SF is especially pertinent in the case of high-strength

concrete (HSC), where it is essential to control the cement content. Generally, a range of 10% to 15% of SF about the total cement content can be effectively utilized.

For most combinations of binders, incorporating SF is a common approach to produce concrete with normal workability while achieving a strength level surpassing 80 N/mm². To ensure the proper dispersion of ultra-fine SF particles, plasticizers should be incorporated into these mixtures. SF can be employed in various forms, including powder, granulates, or slurry (Chan, S.Y.N.; Anson, M.; Koo, S. L.).

2 FIBRE-REINFORCED CONCRETE

2.1 Introduction

The utilisation of fiber reinforcement is not a recent concept. Dating back to around 1500 BC, Egyptians incorporated straws to reinforce mud bricks, preventing them from becoming overly brittle upon drying. In certain regions of China and Japan circa 2000 BC, clay walls were reinforced with thin strips of bamboo. The production of thin sheet cement products reinforced with asbestos fibers, known as the Hatcheck process, has been ongoing since the early 1900s. The roots of concrete reinforced with steel wires and fibers can be traced back to the patents of Joseph Lambot in 1847 and A. Berard in 1874. Since then, an expanding array of fibers including steel, polymeric (such as polypropylene, polyethylene, polyvinyl alcohol, aramid, acrylic, nylon, etc.), and natural fibers (like asbestos, cellulose, sisal, etc.), as well as glass and carbon fibers have been applied to reinforce concrete, mortar, or cement in both continuous and discontinuous forms, employing various processes.

The predominant application of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) involves non-structural purposes or secondary elements. In these cases, fibers are utilised to fulfil functions such as reducing shrinkage cracking and restricting crack widths resulting from mechanical loading. The structural application of FRC is relatively uncommon, and efforts to integrate fiber reinforcement as a structural component have primarily focused on substituting shear-reinforcing stirrups in structural members like beams. Additionally, attempts have been made to replace intricate reinforcement arrangements in regions where concentrated loading is applied to the structure.

Despite extensive research on Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC), its anticipated widespread adoption in the construction industry has not materialized. Several factors contribute to this phenomenon. Conceptually, although FRC is acknowledged for its toughness compared to traditional concrete, the systematic translation of this property into structural performance is notably lacking. The absence of design guidelines makes it challenging for engineers to seamlessly integrate this material into their structural designs. Additionally, there is an ongoing debate about establishing robust test methods that effectively and accurately characterise FRC.

In contrast to conventionally reinforced concrete, which is typically treated as an ideal elastoplastic material characterized by only two parameters – strength and stiffness, Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) is defined by its toughness or softening. In practical terms, FRC often exhibits similar strength and stiffness to plain concrete. Consequently, the establishment of design rules for FRC necessitates the use of fracture mechanics models, addressing the mechanics of crack formation and propagation in the material. For structures constructed from softening materials, the structural behaviour is frequently governed by crack formation. The application of fracture mechanics becomes particularly crucial for structures such as concrete dams and nuclear reactor vessels or containments, where safety concerns are exceptionally high, and the potential consequences of a disaster are enormous.

Fiber Reinforced Concrete (FRC) is essentially a composite material comprising a concrete matrix infused with various types of fibres, which can be dispersed in various manners. The primary motivation behind the development and practical utilization of this composite cementitious material is the enhancement of specific mechanical properties.

Incorporating different fibre types can notably enhance the toughness of concrete. There are three principal orientations of fibres within the hardened concrete mass. The most prevalent orientations include randomly dispersed low-fibre volume (depicted in Figure 13a) or high-fibre volume (as seen in Figure 13b), as exemplified by materials like SIFCON (Balaguru, P. & Kendzulak, J.) and (Lawrence, P.). Less frequent are unidirectional fibre composites consisting of non-metal fibres, as shown in Figure 13c.

In both Normal Strength Concrete (NSC) and High Strength Concrete (HSC), the addition of fibres proves advantageous, bolstering the toughness of the concrete and augmenting other properties of this composite material. In the case of Ultra-High Strength Concrete (UHSC) (as indicated in Table 1), the inclusion of fibres becomes imperative due to the extreme brittleness of UHSC. Without the incorporation of fibres, UHSC cannot be viably employed in practical applications (Walraven, J.C).

HSC exhibits a brittle nature, and as the concrete strength escalates, the post-peak portion of the stress-strain diagram tends to diminish or exhibit a steep decline. This increase in concrete strength inversely impacts its ductility – the higher the concrete's strength, the lower its ductility.

Fig. 13. Three Different Types of Steel Fibre Orientation [8] [9]

2.2 Materials of Fibres

There are several materials of fibres on the market, which vary considerably in properties, effectiveness, and cost. Some common fibres and their typical properties are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Typical Properties of Common Fibres (Walraven, J.C)

Fibre	Diameter (μ m)	Specific gravity	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Strain to Failure (%)
Steel	5 -500	7.84	0.5 - 2	210	0.5 - 3.5
Glass	9 -15	2.60	2.0 – 4.0	70 - 80	2.0 – 3.5
Polypropylene	20 - 200	0.90	0.5 – 0.75	5 - 77	8.0
Cellulose (Kraft)	20 - 120	1.54	0.3 – 0.5	24 - 40	-
Carbon (HS)	9	1.90	2.6	230	1.0
Asbestos (Chrysolite)	0.02 - 30	2.60	3.5	165	2 - 3
PVA -Polyvinyl alcoh	15	1.30	0.9	29	-

2.3 Shapes of Steels

The effectiveness of steel fibre, as a part of a cementitious composite, depends not only on the material used for fibre production. The form and shape of fibres can be different.

Mostly steel fibres can be used in different ways – Steel Fibre Reinforced Concrete (SFRC). Their form depends on production technology (Balaguru, P. & Kendzulak, J.).

2.4 Production Technologies

Steel fibres employed in construction are typically crafted from either carbon steel or alloy steel. Alloy steel fibres are predominantly utilized for their corrosion resistance, making them suitable for applications in refractory environments and marine structures. The manufacturing of steel fibres can be achieved through various methods, as described in references (Mindes, S. & Bentur, A.) and [RILEM-Committee-TDF-162]:

- pulling and successive *cutting* of wires Figure 14a
- milling Figure 14b
- shearing sheets Figure 14c

Fig. 14. Production Technologies of Steel Fibres (RILEM-Committee-TDF-162)

The fibres are generated using the hot melt extraction technique, involving a spinning wheel that contacts the molten steel surface (Walraven, J.C). This contact lifts a portion of the liquid metal, which subsequently solidifies and is ejected in the form of fibres (as depicted in Figure 14d) by the FIBRAFLEX process.

To simplify the process of handling and mixing, certain fibres are grouped in bundles comprising 10-30 fibres. These bundles are bound using a water-soluble adhesive, which dissolves during the mixing process, as seen with the DRAMIX method (RILEM-Committee-TDF-162).

2.5 The Application of the High-Strength Fibre Reinforced Concrete

The storage and disposal of radioactive waste and hazardous materials necessitate stringent containment measures. These measures are essential to isolate such materials from the surrounding environment, ensuring the protection of future generations' quality of life.

Sogefibre's fiber concrete technology was specifically developed to effectively manage radioactive waste. This innovative technology integrates advancements from the prefabricated concrete industry with methodologies employed in the nuclear sector. Its superior performance has been acknowledged by nuclear regulatory authorities and radioactive waste disposal agencies in both France and internationally.

Fibre concrete uses FIBRAFLEX, a highly corrosion-resistant, non-crystalline metal fibre. Fibre concrete products offer several advantages:

- greater bending strength than unreinforced concrete
- less cracking, therefore greater long-term containment
- elimination of corrodible carbon steel rebar

Fiber concrete uses FIBRAFLEX, a non-crystalline metal fiber resistant to corrosion. The advantages of fiber concrete products include:

- Enhanced bending strength compared to unreinforced concrete.
- Reduced cracking, leading to improved long-term containment.
- Elimination of susceptible carbon steel rebar prone to corrosion.

Fibre-reinforced concrete (FRC) containers are designed for the secure disposal of low to medium-level radioactive waste. These containers are tailored for two main categories of waste: Solid waste, including dry active waste, structural components, and materials from dismantling. These wastes, whether compactable or not, are typically immobilized with grout. Concentrates are derived from liquid waste treatment and other homogeneous waste, such as ion exchange resins, incinerator ashes, and waste sludges. These materials are blended with cement and poured into the containers for effective containment Figure 15 and Figure 16.

Parameters of container:

- A - Vent or filling hole
- B - Lid to be sealed
- C - Gripping area
- D - Rough surfaces

Fig. 15. Description of the container

Tab. 3. Dimensions of Container

Container	Dimensions exterior	Dimensions interior
Height (mm)	1700	1445
Width (mm)	1700	1450
Length (mm)	1700	1450
Capacity (liters)	5100	3058

Minimum wall thickness: 100 mm, weight: 4275 kg

During prolonged storage or final disposal, container walls must withstand both mechanical stress and ensure effective radionuclide containment. The walls of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) containers have been meticulously designed to endure for 300 years, even under the most challenging conditions. Beyond this timeframe, the radioactivity of the waste within the container will have decayed to negligible levels.

With HSFC, the reinforcing of shotcrete is shot with the concrete, thus eliminating the shadow problem, and speeding up production. HSFC provides more uniform reinforcement throughout the entire shotcrete mass, thus allowing for thinner sections on very irregular surfaces.

Steel Fibre Reinforced Shotcrete (SFRC) has been successfully used to repair dams, spillways, caissons, bulkheads, culverts, piers, locks, inverts, piles, columns, water tanks, aqueducts, tunnels, and refractories.

Fig. 16. Realized container from High strength fiber reinforced concrete

Precast concrete producers are using HSFC to eliminate pattern cracking, reduce chipping and cracking in handling units, increase performance in corrosive environments, resist thermal shock and impact and minimize cracking in casting beads.

Many different sizes and shapes of precast units are utilizing HSFC to eliminate congested steel rebar and mesh.

The primary HSFC slab applications are for factory floors, industrial floors where damaging dynamic and concentrated loads require added reinforcing, and commercial floors where crack and fatigue resistance are needed. Pavement uses include highways, roads, parking areas, bridge decks, thin-bonded overlays, airport runways, aprons, and truck weight stations.

During an earthquake, conventional reinforced concrete first loses the concrete cover over the rebar. With HSFC there is very little spalling and much more energy is needed to lose the concrete wedged in between the rebar. In HSFC the fibres add a toughness that maintains better structural stiffness, which makes safer buildings in earthquake zones.

3. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the choice between high-strength concrete (HSC) and high-strength fibre concrete (HSFC) depends on the specific requirements of a construction project. HSC excels in applications where compressive strength is paramount, while HSFC provides a well-rounded solution with superior tensile and flexural strength, making it ideal for projects where cracking and long-term durability are significant concerns.

The main difference in behaviour between plain and FRC is the toughness, i.e., the ability to support loads even after the formation of cracks, this phenomenon results from the fibres that span across the cracked matrix, shouldering the local stresses until they are eventually either pulled out or fractured under additional load. This post-cracking process is governed by many parameters such as fibre length, diameter, mechanical properties, volume concentration, orientation, concrete matrix properties etc. It is many design parameters that for the conventional design approach, which is accustomed to two parameters - strength and stiffness of concrete, appear to be an overwhelming task. Therefore, fracture mechanic models must be used to establish design rules for FRC that take the softening behaviour into account.

The growing success of fibre-reinforced concrete has led to a variety of fibres being offered on the construction market. But unlike conventional reinforcement concrete, for which properties of the various types are well known and outlined in standards, no general design rules exist for arbitrary types of fibre concrete, except steel fibre reinforced concrete, where extensive research has taken place for many years. This lack of design guidelines for fibre-reinforced concrete in general helps to explain the confusion that often accompanies designing with different fibres.

Steel fibre concrete as a construction material is gaining more and more prominence in the construction industry, This is mainly related to the expanding range of fibre reinforcement in the building materials market. Foreign and domestic companies offer fibre reinforcement with improved properties. In recent times, fibre reinforcement for concrete has started to be used in the form of a "cocktail" of different types of fibres in terms of material, shape and size.

The use of steel fibre concrete is also related to better knowledge of its mechanical and physical properties. The degree of their knowledge has changed significantly over the past years. Fibre concrete is still the subject of intensive research and finds new possibilities of use not only in construction but also in new possibilities of use.

The growing success of fibre-reinforced concrete has led to a variety of fibres being offered on the construction market. But unlike conventional reinforcement concrete, for which properties of the various types are well known and outlined in standards, no general design rules exist for arbitrary types of fibre concrete, except steel fibre reinforced concrete, where extensive research has taken place for many years. This lack of design guidelines for fibre-reinforced concrete in general helps to explain the confusion that often accompanies designing with different fibres.

The primary distinction in behaviour between plain concrete and Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) lies in toughness specifically, the ability to bear loads even after the formation of cracks. This quality is attributed to the fibers, which bridge the cracked matrix and carry local stresses until they are either pulled out or broken under further loading. The post-cracking process is influenced by various parameters such as fiber length, diameter, mechanical properties, volume concentration, orientation, concrete matrix properties, and more. Given the multitude of design parameters, traditional approaches accustomed to considering only the strength and stiffness of concrete find handling these variables overwhelming. Consequently, fracture mechanic models must be employed to establish design rules for FRC, accounting for its softening behaviour.

The incorporation of steel fibers, into concrete, enhances its mechanical properties and durability. When dealing with radioactive waste storage, it's crucial to ensure the structural integrity and long-term performance of the containment system.

The addition of fibers increases the tensile strength of concrete, which is particularly important for structures that may be subjected to loading and stress over time.

FRC also enhances the durability of concrete, reducing the likelihood of cracking and deterioration, which is crucial for maintaining the containment of radioactive materials.

Fibers in the concrete help control the formation and propagation of cracks. This is important for preventing the release of radioactive materials due to cracks in the containment structure.

FRC can have lower permeability compared to conventional concrete. This is important for minimizing the potential for water ingress, which can affect the stability of the containment structure and the integrity of radioactive waste storage.

The addition of fibers improves the ductility of concrete, allowing it to deform and absorb energy before failure. This can be crucial in preventing sudden and catastrophic failure of the containment structure.

Steel fibers can provide additional radiation shielding. This can be beneficial for structures that need to protect workers and the environment from radiation emitted by the stored waste.

The improved durability and crack resistance of FRC can result in reduced maintenance needs over the lifespan of the storage facility, which is crucial for minimizing the risks associated with radioactive waste storage.

It's important to note that the design and construction of structures for radioactive waste storage involve careful consideration of various factors, including the specific type and characteristics of the waste, regulatory requirements, and long-term performance expectations. Additionally, the use of fibre-reinforced concrete should be part of a comprehensive approach to ensure the safety and security of radioactive waste storage facilities.

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